

Catalogue of Criteria for Assessing the Funding Eligibility of Open Science Infrastructures

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This criteria catalogue has been developed by a working group of KEMÖ (Kooperation E-Medien Österreich, the Austrian Academic Library Consortium).

It is designed to support research institutions and organisations in evaluating Open Science Infrastructures¹. The 20 criteria can be used to make informed decisions regarding financial support for Open Science Infrastructures. Explanatory texts are provided to assist with the assessment of some of the criteria.

Open Science Infrastructures are evaluated on the basis of *relevance*, *costs*, *sustainability*, *transparency*, and *innovation* (categories 1–5). A decision about financial support can then be made based on these analyses. The category consortial funding (6) can be added when considering joint funding by multiple organisations.

The catalogue is not based on a quantitative evaluation system but is intended to enable structured reflection on key aspects of an Open Science Infrastructure.

Not all criteria are applicable to all types of infrastructures. The more criteria an infrastructure fulfils, the more favourably it can be evaluated. If a criterion turns out to be not relevant to an infrastructure, this should not be seen as a drawback.

If support for an infrastructure is under consideration but information on a relevant criterion cannot be found, the document “Assessment Questions for Open Science Infrastructures” (supplement) can be sent directly to the respective infrastructure.

A lack of response to multiple questions may indicate that it is inadvisable to fund the infrastructure. A mission statement of the infrastructure is helpful when reviewing the criteria.

The criteria from the [Principles of Open Scholarly Infrastructures](#) or the [OA Sustainability Index](#) can also be applied. The infrastructure should achieve at least Grade 3 if the OA Sustainability Index is used.

¹ For a definition of Open Science Infrastructures, see UNESCO [Recommendation on Open Science - Legal Affairs](#)

If an Open Science Infrastructure has already been evaluated through platforms such as [SCOSS](#) or [Infra Finder](#), the data collected there can assist in completing the assessment.

Categories:

1. Relevance
2. Costs
3. Sustainability
4. Transparency
5. Innovation
6. Consortial funding

1. Relevance	
1.1. The infrastructure is supported by established and trustworthy institutions/scientists.	
1.2. The scholarly community considers the infrastructure important to the advancement of the discipline.	This refers to a community of researchers and/or librarians (or research support staff).
1.3. Content is quality-assured, for instance, through selection criteria or review processes.	For example, through initial and/or ongoing quality control of indexed sources such as articles, journals, repositories or other data.
1.4. Evidence is provided demonstrating the added value.	For example, statistics or reports that demonstrate added value, as well as blog posts by experts.

2. Costs	
2.1. The infrastructure's costs (e.g., personnel, operations, service) are itemised transparently at least once a year, and it adheres to the principles of economy and efficiency.	Documentation of expenditure.
2.2. The infrastructure has a strategy for sustainable/long-term financing.	Documentation of revenue.
2.3. The infrastructure is a not-for-profit organisation.	No profit should be distributed; additional income should be reinvested (except when building up reserves).

3. Sustainability	
3.1. The infrastructure has a long-term (3–5 year) plan for its strategic and technical development.	Particularly relevant for new infrastructure.
3.2. The infrastructure declares itself to be 'open' (e.g., open source) and reusable.	For example, in a mission statement.
3.3. Open licences are used for the content (ideally CC BY or CC 0). The metadata is machine-readable.	This refers to data and metadata.
3.4. Existing community standards/persistent identifiers are used.	For example, DOI, ORCID or metadata schemata.

4. Transparency	
4.1. The infrastructure has transparent ownership and governance (decision-making and participation structures).	Operating institution(s) or legal structures such as associations, limited companies or foundations are evident.
4.2. The infrastructure publishes its goals and services transparently on its website.	
4.3. The infrastructure discloses which user data it collects and for what purpose.	For example, personal data or IP addresses/cookies.

5. Innovation	
5.1. The infrastructure offers special/important/novel services within the research life cycle.	This refers to innovative functionalities that create added value for researchers, librarians, institutions, etc.
5.2. The infrastructure contributes to the advancement of Open Science.	For example, by supporting and enabling the implementation of Open Science practices.

6. Consortial funding	
6.1. There is interest in consortial funding from several institutions.	
6.2. The consortium partners benefit from strategic, administrative, or financial savings or added value.	
6.3. The infrastructure can conclude bilateral agreements with individual consortial partners.	
6.4. The infrastructure is prepared to issue invoices directly to the institutions.	If a collective invoice is a requirement, the infrastructure must be willing to involve an agency for reimbursement.